

Removal of Antimony from its Solutions by Nitric Acid.

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The determination of the solubilities in aqueous nitric acid of various concentrations of Sb_2O_3 , Sb_2O_4 , Sb_2O_5 and of the residue left when antimony salts are treated repeatedly with strong HNO_3 , was undertaken with a view to find out how far antimony could be completely removed from its solutions by treatment with HNO_3 .

Antimony in each of the extracts was determined by the usual bromate method. The residue (*cf.* columns 5 and 6 of the table) was analysed for antimony by Sn and HCl method, and water by absorption in $CaCl_2$ tubes and was found to be $Sb_2O_5, 2H_2O$, when dried at 120° and $3 Sb_2O_5, 2H_2O$ when dried at 160° .

HNO ₃ conc.	Antimony oxide in a litre of the acid extract at 100°			Sb ₂ O ₅ in a litre of the acid extract at 100° of the residue dried	
	Sb ₂ O ₃	Sb ₂ O ₄	Sb ₂ O ₅	at 120°	at 160°
1 N	647·15 mg.	146·28 mg.	256·5 mg.	359·10 mg.	297·50 mg.
2	739·60	126·78	153·9	307·80	128·25
4	1119·40	48·76	56·4	241·10	97·47
6	1479·20	19·50	20·5	35·91	30·78
8	1294·30	Nil	Nil	5·03	Nil
10	1294·30	"	"	Nil	"
12	1294·30	"	"	"	"
16	1201·85	"	"	"	"

From the above table, it will be seen that Sb_2O_4 and Sb_2O_5 remain practically insoluble in HNO_3 of concentration above 6N; even Sb_2O_3 is but sparingly soluble. The residue, too, whether dried at 120° or at 160° is not dissolved by HNO_3 above 8N. It is clear, therefore, that antimony can be quantitatively removed by repeated treatment and extraction with concentrated HNO_3 and the method can be utilised for separating tin and antimony together from other bases as insoluble oxides in qualitative analysis.

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